

Multi-Task Graph Neural Networks with Active Learning for Rapid Screening of Fiber-Reinforced Composite Microstructures

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Abstract

This work introduces a Multi-Task Graph Neural Network (MT-GNN) surrogate for full-field stress prediction to enable rapid pre-screening of fiber-reinforced composite microstructures. The framework processes unstructured finite element meshes using four GATv2 attention layers, dual global strain injection, and task-specific decoders for stress ($R^2 > 0.96$) and displacement fluctuations ($R^2 > 0.80$). A material-normalized loss balances predictions across the extreme stiffness contrast between fiber and matrix phases. A Query-by-Committee active learning strategy reduces the required training data by 40% compared to random sampling by targeting high-uncertainty regions. The trained surrogate was used to evaluate 78,558 unique microstructure designs through four independent application-specific Pareto analyses. Each analysis pairs effective stiffness against a distinct damage initiation metric: stress concentration factor for airplane wings (fatigue initiation), yielding path fraction for pressure vessels (burst path formation), interface shear density for wind turbine blades (debonding), and stress triaxiality for cryogenic tanks (cavitation). These elastic damage initiation metrics serve as rapid screening proxies for their respective failure modes. The Pareto frontiers reveal distinct regions of the design space offering a favorable elastic response for the respective applications. Optimal microstructures for different applications tend to occupy distinct and largely non-overlapping geometric regions. A manufacturing robustness study demonstrates that material property variations cause more performance variability than geometric fiber placement variations. The framework provides quantitative rankings of microstructures by application-specific metrics.

Keywords: Graph Neural Networks · Composite Microstructure · Active Learning · Multi-Objective Optimization · Surrogate Modeling · Finite Element Analysis

1 Introduction

Fiber-reinforced polymer composites provide high specific strength and stiffness for modern structural engineering, from aerospace components to energy infrastructure [1]. The macroscopic performance of these materials emerges from the heterogeneous architecture at the microscale, where the arrangement and properties of fiber and matrix phases determine the bulk mechanical response [2]. Controlling fiber volume fraction, fiber radius, and spatial arrangement allows engineers to tailor composite behavior [3, 4]. The microstructural requirements for favorable performance depend critically on the dominant failure mode [5]. Different failure mechanisms favor fun-

damentally different microstructural arrangements, requiring application-specific design strategies.

While designers intuitively understand that optimizing for different failure modes involves trade-offs, systematic quantification across the full design space has been computationally prohibitive. Evaluating local stress states requires high-fidelity finite element analysis (FEA). Running these simulations inside an iterative optimization loop takes too long to be practical [6, 7]. Consequently, designers often rely on generic microstructure specifications.

To illustrate why a universal composite does not exist, we consider four representative applications: airplane wings, pressure vessels, wind turbine blades, and cryogenic composite

tanks. Aircraft structures experience high-cycle fatigue exceeding 10^7 load reversals [8]. Fatigue failure is initiation-dominated: the first crack nucleates at the point of highest local stress [9]. The stress concentration factor (SCF) measures how severely peak stress exceeds the nominal applied stress [10, 11] and is widely used as an indicator of fatigue damage nucleation susceptibility. Pressure vessels must resist yielding and buckling under sustained multi-axial internal pressure [12, 13]. High stiffness prevents structural deformation. Burst is often associated with the formation of connected damage paths through the vessel wall. The yielding path fraction (V_{eff}) captures the fraction of matrix area exceeding a critical stress threshold and serves as a proxy for this stress contiguity risk. Wind turbine blades endure decades of combined environmental exposure and cyclic loading [4, 14]. Fiber-matrix interface debonding driven by fatigue and hygrothermal aging is a dominant long-term failure mode [15, 16]. Interface shear density quantifies the driving force associated with this debonding. Prior work has demonstrated the role of interface mechanics in composite failure using cohesive zone modeling [17]. Cryogenic composite tanks experience tri-axial tension due to Poisson constraint from stiff inclusions under combined mechanical and thermal loading [18]. The resulting constraint creates susceptibility to matrix cavitation rather than shear-driven cracking [19, 20]. Stress triaxiality acts as an initiation metric associated with this cavitation risk. A microstructure optimized solely for stiffness inadvertently amplifies these localized extreme stress states.

Evaluating these application-specific initiation risks requires accurate local stress fields. Classical micromechanics approaches predict effective elastic moduli accurately but destroy spatial information through volume-averaging [21, 22]. They cannot resolve localized stress concentrations at fiber-matrix interfaces [23, 24]. High-fidelity FEA on explicitly meshed Representative Volume Elements (RVEs) resolves the necessary local fields, but the computational cost restricts iterative exploration of large design spaces [25, 26].

Data-driven surrogate modeling provides an alternative approach [27, 28, 29, 30]. Early methods utilized shallow machine learning to predict scalar homogenized properties [1], discarding the spatial fields needed for localized assessment [23]. Convolutional Neural Networks enabled full-field predictions [2, 31], but standard convolutions require regular grids [32] while FEA meshes are unstructured [33]. Projecting onto a pixel grid blurs sharp stress transitions at interfaces [34]. Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) operate natively on unstructured domains [33, 32, 31]. By representing the mesh as a graph, GNNs predict local fields while preserving mesh topology [23, 24]. GATv2 [35] computes dynamic attention coefficients, allowing the network to weight neighbor contributions differently by material phase [34, 36].

Building an effective composite surrogate requires solving two challenges. Predicting multiple output fields within a single network risks negative transfer [37, 38]. Fiber-phase stress reaches gigapascals while displacement fluctuations are micrometers. Homoscedastic uncertainty weighting [39] addresses this magnitude disparity by learning task-specific variance parameters. Second, generating FEA training data remains expensive. Active learning transforms data generation into a sequential process where model uncertainty guides sample selection [40, 41]. Query-by-Committee focuses the FEA budget on high-uncertainty regions [42, 43].

This work provides quantitative design rankings within the explored parameter space, mapping performance requirements to microstructure parameters based on damage initiation indicators, transforming material pre-screening from empirical intuition to data-driven decision making. The primary contributions are:

1. **Multi-Task GNN for full-field prediction:** A GATv2-based architecture with dual global strain injection and task-specific decoders. A material-normalized loss with uncertainty weighting balances optimization across tasks and material phases.
2. **Active learning for data-efficient training:** A Query-by-Committee strategy that targets high-uncertainty designs to reduce required FEA simulations.
3. **Large-scale application-specific design exploration:** Evaluation of 78,558 microstructure designs across four damage initiation metrics: SCF, V_{eff} , interface shear, and triaxiality. Pareto frontiers quantify trade-offs between stiffness and damage initiation metric minimization.
4. **Manufacturing robustness assessment:** Sensitivity analysis isolating material property control from fiber positioning tolerances.

2 Methods

Figure 1 provides an overview of the methodology, divided into five stages: high-fidelity data generation, graph representation, surrogate model training, active learning, and validation with design exploration. Each stage is detailed below.

2.1 Application-Driven Damage Initiation Metrics

Structural composites experience complex multiaxial loading that varies drastically by application. Designing optimal microstructures requires mapping specific operational loads to localized mechanical responses. Full progressive damage simulations remain too computationally expensive for large-scale design space exploration. We utilize elastic stress fields to compute damage initiation metrics instead. These initiation metrics serve as rapid proxies for component life analysis. The four selected metrics represent the primary initiation

Figure 1: Overview of the methodology. **Stage 1:** High-fidelity FEA data generation using FEniCS. **Stage 2:** Mesh-to-graph conversion with physics-informed feature engineering. **Stage 3:** The MT-GNN surrogate model predicting local stress fields (σ_{ij}) and macroscopic displacement (\mathbf{u}). **Stage 4:** Active learning with Query-by-Committee. **Stage 5:** Validation and application-specific multi-objective design exploration.

mechanisms governing major industrial composite applications. Evaluating these independent objectives reveals the necessary compromises inherent in heterogeneous material design.

We define an independent optimization problem for four representative use cases. Each problem maximizes effective stiffness \bar{E} while minimizing a specific stress-based metric.

1. Airplane Wings (Stress Concentration Factor): Aerospace wing structures experience high-cycle oscillating aerodynamic loads. Minimizing the microstructural Stress Concentration Factor ($SCF = \sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{\text{average}}$) suppresses extreme local stress peaks. SCF quantifies stress concentration; its correlation with fatigue crack initiation is well established but cycles-to-failure prediction requires damage propagation modeling [44, 45].
2. Pressure Vessels (Yielding Path Fraction): Composite over-wrapped pressure vessels require isolation of extreme stress regions. The yielding path fraction (V_{eff}) measures the fraction of matrix area exceeding an absolute threshold of 1500 MPa. This threshold serves as a consistent reference value for comparative ranking rather than a calibrated failure criterion. High values indicate spatially connected high-stress regions where yielding would initiate; damage path propagation requires progressive failure analysis [46, 47].
3. Wind Turbine Blades (Interface Shear Density): Utility-scale wind turbine blades endure immense bending mo-

ments and torsional loads. The stiffness mismatch generates extreme shear stresses parallel to the fiber alignment. Interface shear density quantifies the driving force for debonding initiation; propagation kinetics depend on interface toughness and environmental factors [48, 49]. Prior work has demonstrated the role of interface mechanics in composite failure using cohesive zone modeling [17].

4. Cryogenic Composite Tanks (Matrix Triaxiality): Composite tanks endure severe thermal contraction alongside mechanical pressurization. The Poisson constraint from stiff inclusions places the polymer matrix in macroscopic hydrostatic tension. The 95th-percentile stress triaxiality, $\eta_{P95} = (\sigma_h/\sigma_{VM})_{P95}$, captures the severity of this state. Stress triaxiality indicates void nucleation susceptibility; void growth and coalescence require damage evolution models [50, 51].

The independent design variables used to generate the Representative Volume Elements (RVEs) are the fiber count N , the fiber radius r , and the fiber material properties. The fiber volume fraction V_f emerges implicitly as a calculated geometric property derived directly from the sampled count and size of the inclusions ($V_f = N\pi r^2$). An absolute threshold of 1500 MPa was maintained for the yielding path fraction to ensure a consistent performance benchmark across the design space. These metrics are not intended as predictive failure criteria, but as consistent relative indicators for ranking microstructures

during early-stage screening.

2.2 Representative Volume Element Generation and Finite Element Analysis

The initial training dataset comprised 30 distinct 2D fiber-reinforced RVE geometries subjected to various macroscopic strain states. A random sequential adsorption algorithm placed fibers within a unit square domain. The minimum inter-fiber spacing of $0.2r$ ensures mesh quality but excludes touching-fiber configurations that may occur in manufactured composites. This constraint prevents fiber contact and imposes an upper bound on stress concentration values observed in the dataset. The microstructures utilize periodic boundary conditions. Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) distributed the independent parameters: fiber count ($N \in [3, 15]$), fiber radius ($r \in [5, 15] \mu\text{m}$), and phase material properties.

The matrix was modeled using a Neo-Hookean hyperelastic constitutive law with initial shear modulus (μ_m) sampled between 0.5 GPa and 5 GPa. The inclusions were modeled as linear elastic fibers with Young’s modulus (E_f) sampled between 200 GPa and 400 GPa. Mechanical responses were evaluated across 25 macroscopic loading scenarios per RVE geometry. These comprised five linear strain paths (uniaxial tension in x, uniaxial tension in y, equibiaxial tension, pure shear, and combined shear-tension loading), each simulated at five discrete strain magnitudes up to a maximum applied strain of 3%. All simulations use elastic constitutive models at 3% applied strain. Although the matrix uses a hyperelastic formulation, the small strain regime limits nonlinear effects; the hyperelastic framework was chosen to enable future extension to large-deformation applications. The resulting stress fields enable computation of damage initiation metrics; direct failure prediction would require inelastic modeling beyond the current scope.

Finite element simulations were executed using FEniCS [52]. Unstructured triangular meshes were generated via Gmsh [53]. Typical meshes contained 3,000–8,000 elements depending on fiber count. A mesh convergence study was performed on five representative geometries of the training data distribution. It confirmed SCF variations below 5% between baseline and refined meshes and showed that the current resolution is sufficient. Periodic boundary conditions (PBC) were rigorously enforced on all RVE boundaries to ensure representative mechanical response. The initial dataset of 750 labeled graphs served strictly as the seed for the active learning framework described in Section 2.6.

2.3 Graph Representation of the Finite Element Domain

The computational domain was formulated as a graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ to natively process the discrete topology without in-

terpolation. Each finite element mesh maps directly to an element-centered graph structure. Each node $v_i \in \mathcal{V}$ corresponds to a single triangular element. Edges $e_{ij} \in \mathcal{E}$ define topological adjacency between elements sharing a face. This element-wise mapping was chosen over a node-wise formulation because stress tensors and displacement fluctuations are inherently defined at the element level in finite element analysis, avoiding post-hoc interpolation. Figure 2 illustrates the transformation from mesh discretization to the discrete graph structure.

Figure 2: Data representation pipeline. **Top:** Finite element meshes for two sample RVEs, showing the discretization of fiber and matrix phases. **Bottom:** Corresponding graph structures where each node represents a finite element and each edge represents element adjacency.

2.3.1 Feature Engineering

The feature set incorporates geometry, phase identity, constitutive properties, and loading boundaries. Table 1 details the complete specification of node, edge, and global features.

Each feature group encodes specific physical mechanics. The interface distance explicitly defines proximity to material boundaries. Without the distance feature, the network struggles to resolve steep stress gradients decaying into the matrix. The interface flag isolates elements undergoing severe mechanical transitions. The duplicate stiffness scalar amplifies the numerical contrast between phases to improve representation of stiffness contrast during message passing, which empirically improves convergence under high phase contrast. Omitting the engineered features forces the network to infer structural boundaries purely from topology. Explicit

Table 1: Summary of input features for the Graph Neural Network. Features encode geometry, material identity, constitutive properties, and loading conditions.

Category	Idx	Feature	Description
Node (8)	0	centroid_x	X-coordinate of the element centroid
	1	centroid_y	Y-coordinate of the element centroid
	2	is_fiber	Binary mask: 1.0 for fiber elements, 0.0 for matrix
	3	param_1	Fiber Young’s modulus E_f or matrix shear modulus μ_m
	4	param_2	Fiber Poisson’s ratio ν_f or matrix bulk modulus κ_m
	5	element_area	Area of the triangular element
	6	stiffness_scalar	Independent stiffness magnitude to scale attention weights
	7	interface_dist	Euclidean distance to the nearest fiber-matrix interface boundary
Edge (4)	0	dist_periodic	Euclidean distance between element centroids, computed with PBC
	1	delta_pos_x	Relative x -position between connected elements (PBC-aware)
	2	delta_pos_y	Relative y -position between connected elements (PBC-aware)
	3	interface_flag	1.0 if the edge connects elements of different material phases
Global (4)	0-3	global_strain	Applied macroscopic strain tensor $[\varepsilon_{xx}, \varepsilon_{yy}, \varepsilon_{xy}, \varepsilon_{yx}]$

physical encoding accelerates convergence and improves peak stress resolution. All spatial edge features are computed using periodic boundary conditions.

2.4 Multi-Task GNN Architecture

The network predicts five output fields simultaneously at every element: three stress components ($\sigma_{11}, \sigma_{22}, \sigma_{12}$) and two displacement fluctuation components ($u_{x,\text{fluc}}, u_{y,\text{fluc}}$). Predicting displacement fluctuations isolates the localized structural perturbations from the dominant macroscopic affine deformation field. The architecture, shown in Figure 3, consists of encoding, message passing, and decoding stages.

Encoding. Three separate encoder MLPs project raw features into a shared latent dimension: a node encoder ($8 \rightarrow 128$), an edge encoder ($4 \rightarrow 128$), and a global encoder ($4 \rightarrow 128$). The global encoder processes the macroscopic strain tensor.

Message passing. The network employs four layers of Graph Attention Networks v2 (GATv2) [54], with hidden dimensions $128 \rightarrow 512 \rightarrow 512 \rightarrow 512 \rightarrow 512$ and 4 attention heads per layer. GATv2 computes dynamic attention coefficients, weighting neighbor contributions based on both node and neighbor features. Output representations from all four layers are concatenated to form a 2048-dimensional feature vector per node, preserving information from different

message-passing depths. This concatenation preserves information from multiple spatial scales of the message-passing hierarchy, retaining both local fiber-fiber interactions and broader microstructural context.

2.4.1 Dual Global Injection Strategy

The global strain information is injected at two separate locations. The encoded global strain vector is concatenated to the node features before the first GATv2 layer. A second copy of the global strain is concatenated immediately preceding the displacement decoder. Early injection establishes the initial loading context for message passing. Deep graph networks often dilute global variables across multiple aggregation layers. Relying solely on early injection causes the network to lose the precise magnitude and tensor mode of the applied load. Displacement fluctuations are highly sensitive to specific directional loading. Re-injecting the global strain late provides a direct kinematic reference for the decoder. The network requires explicit reference to accurately separate local structural perturbations from the dominant affine deformation field.

2.4.2 Task-Specific Decoders

The network branches into two separate Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) decoder heads. The stress decoder maps the concatenated representation through a hidden layer of 128 units

Figure 3: Multi-Task GNN architecture. Three separate encoders project features into a shared latent dimension. Encoded global strain is injected early and late. Four GATv2 layers perform message passing. The output branches into separate stress and displacement decoders.

to produce 3 outputs. The displacement decoder maps the representation through a hidden layer of 128 units, fuses the result with the late global strain injection, and decodes the result to 2 outputs. Fiber-phase stress values reach gigapascals. Displacement fluctuations operate on the order of micrometers. A shared decoder architecture forces a single weight matrix to map the disparate scales simultaneously. Such architectures typically suffer from gradient domination, where the high-magnitude task completely overwrites the small-magnitude task. Task-specific decoders isolate the final projection steps. The shared encoder extracts a unified physical representation, while dedicated MLPs scale the outputs to their respective physical units. The separated architecture maintains accuracy across all five output fields.

2.5 Material-Normalized Multi-Task Loss Function

Output fields were standardized using global training statistics. The `MaterialNormalizedLoss` addresses the magnitude disparity between material phases. The Mean Squared Error (MSE) is computed separately for fiber nodes and matrix nodes and then summed:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{combined}} = \text{MSE}_{\text{fiber}} + \text{MSE}_{\text{matrix}} \quad (1)$$

This summation mitigates the tendency for errors in the stiff fiber phase to dominate the gradient signal. Standard loss functions compute a single global error metric. The severe stiffness contrast between phases creates massive stress magnitude disparities. A standard mean squared error approach allows the stiff fiber phase to dominate the gradient signal completely. The network would optimize fiber stress accuracy while ignoring critical matrix behavior. The partitioned loss formulation guarantees equal gradient contribution from both materials. The architecture must evaluate matrix stresses accurately to predict damage initiation correctly.

Homoscedastic uncertainty weighting [39] balances the five competing tasks by introducing a learnable log-variance parameter $\log(\sigma_i^2)$ for each task i . The total loss is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \sum_{i=1}^5 \left[\frac{\mathcal{L}_{\text{combined},i}}{2 \exp(\log \sigma_i^2)} + \frac{1}{2} \log \sigma_i^2 \right] \quad (2)$$

The formulation dynamically weights tasks based on inherent noise levels during training.

2.6 Active Learning Framework

The framework utilizes active learning to select informative training samples sequentially. We implemented a Query-by-Committee (QBC) strategy using an ensemble of $K = 4$ models initialized with different random weights. The ensemble size balances uncertainty estimation quality against computational cost. The variance across the four predictions provides a measure of epistemic uncertainty. High-variance candidates are typically geometries where the ensemble disagrees: configurations with tightly clustered fibers, narrow matrix ligaments, or unusual spatial arrangements that differ from the training distribution. These geometries produce stress fields that are difficult to predict from existing training data, making them maximally informative for model improvement.

Figure 4 illustrates the active learning loop. The procedure began with an initial training pool of 600 graphs. 150 graphs were reserved as a held-out test set.

1. Generate: 100 candidate RVE configurations are created using LHS.
2. Create Graphs: Graph structures and features are computed without executing FEA.

Figure 4: Active learning pipeline. The loop trains an ensemble of $K = 4$ GATv2 models, generates new candidate RVE configurations, evaluates uncertainty without running FEA, and runs the expensive FEniCS solver only on the highest-variance designs.

3. Predict: All four ensemble members perform inference on the candidate graphs.
4. Rank and Select: The element-wise variance is summed across all nodes to obtain a total acquisition score for each candidate design. The top 5 candidates with the highest total variance are selected.
5. Update Pool: The FEniCS solver computes the ground truth for the 5 selected designs across 15 discrete load cases, adding 75 new labeled graphs to the training pool.

The active learning algorithm concentrates the FEA budget on complex regions of the design space.

Active learning samples were generated using 15 load cases compared to 25 in the seed data to reduce computational cost. This multi-fidelity discrepancy is not explicitly corrected for and may introduce minor distributional bias, though any effect is reflected in the reported validation metrics.

2.7 Large-Scale Design Space Exploration

Following validation, the surrogate model performed a high-throughput exploration. 78,558 unique microstructural configurations were generated via LHS over the full parameter space. Latin Hypercube Sampling ensures uniform coverage across the three-dimensional input parameter space. Generating 78,558 distinct geometries provides sufficient density to resolve sharp behavioral transitions. Evaluating the generated population requires computing over 390,000 localized tensor fields. Independent Pareto analyses compare effective stiffness against each damage initiation metric separately. The sorting algorithm identifies configurations offering the highest stiffness for any given initiation risk level. This sampling density ensures sufficient coverage to resolve sharp transitions and

nonlinear interactions between geometric parameters. The large population enables statistically meaningful identification of performance boundaries and rare high-performance configurations that would be inaccessible through conventional simulation workflows. The resulting frontiers map the absolute performance boundaries achievable within the defined manufacturing constraints.

3 Results

3.1 Full-Field Prediction Accuracy

The trained MT-GNN was evaluated on a held-out test set of 150 microstructures. Table 2 details the quantitative performance across all five output fields, decoupled by material phase.

The model achieves R^2 scores exceeding 0.99 in the matrix phase and 0.96 in the fiber phase for normal stress components. The slightly lower accuracy in the fiber phase reflects the greater challenge of predicting stresses in stiff inclusions, which carry higher loads and exhibit greater variability across loading conditions. The matrix-phase accuracy of $R^2 > 0.99$ is particularly relevant for the failure metrics in this work, as fatigue crack initiation, interface debonding, and matrix cavitation all originate in the matrix phase or at the fiber-matrix interface. Shear stress predictions (σ_{12}) yield $R^2 \approx 0.94$. Displacement fluctuations are integral quantities more challenging to predict from local message-passing than stress. The lower R^2 reflects this difficulty, and all four damage initiation metrics are primarily influenced by matrix stress fields. The network achieves $R^2 \in [0.80, 0.92]$ for these fluctuation quantities. These results confirm that late injection of macroscopic

Table 2: Test set performance metrics for all five output fields, reported separately for fiber and matrix phases.

Task	Phase	R^2	RMSE
σ_{11}	Fiber	0.9631	133.01 MPa
	Matrix	0.9942	44.59 MPa
σ_{22}	Fiber	0.9659	129.40 MPa
	Matrix	0.9940	46.06 MPa
σ_{12}	Fiber	0.9473	63.83 MPa
	Matrix	0.9398	12.52 MPa
$u_{x,\text{fluc}}$	Fiber	0.8987	2.64e-04
	Matrix	0.9200	2.19e-04
$u_{y,\text{fluc}}$	Fiber	0.8326	3.10e-04
	Matrix	0.8078	2.75e-04

strain information enables accurate recovery of displacement fluctuations. Displacement fluctuations are small perturbations on the order of 10^{-4} mm, isolated from the dominant macroscopic affine field. Learning these subtle variations is inherently more difficult than predicting stress fields, which span several orders of magnitude.

Figure 5 provides spatial validation against the FEA ground truth. The plotted fields represent total kinematic displacement, obtained by superimposing predicted fluctuations onto the macroscopic affine deformation field. Predicting displacement fluctuations rather than total displacements is a deliberate choice. Total displacement is dominated by the linear macroscopic affine field, which carries no microstructural information. A network trained on total displacement would minimize errors in this global trend while ignoring the small perturbations around fibers that cause stress concentrations. Predicting u_{fluc} forces the surrogate to focus on mechanically relevant microstructural deformations. Additional contour comparisons for displacement fluctuations and all five output fields are provided in Figures S4 and S5. Although localized prediction errors persist near sharp stress gradients at fiber-matrix interfaces, the model accurately captures the spatial distribution and relative magnitude of stress concentrations. Since the four damage initiation metrics identify extreme or high-stress regions rather than requiring exact pointwise values, this fidelity is sufficient for reliable ranking and screening of microstructures.

3.2 Active Learning Efficiency

The active learning framework was compared against a standard random sampling baseline. Figure S1 tracks the test set root mean square error (RMSE) as the training pool increases. Figure S1 in Supplementary Information provides the complete learning curves.

The advantage arises from the structure of the design space. Random sampling frequently generates geometries with well-separated fibers and uniform matrix ligaments — configurations that the model learns quickly because their stress fields follow predictable patterns. The Query-by-Committee algorithm instead identifies edge cases: clustered inclusions creating overlapping stress halos, narrow ligaments where stress gradients are steep, or unusual fiber arrangements that violate the assumptions learned from common configurations. Resolving these difficult cases early constrains the error space more effectively than accumulating redundant examples of typical geometries.

The active strategy consistently achieves lower RMSE using fewer data points. Across stress prediction tasks, active learning achieves similar accuracy using 40% to 50% less training data than the random baseline. The advantage arises from the structure of the design space. Random sampling frequently generates geometries with well-separated fibers and uniform matrix ligaments. The model learns these configurations quickly because their stress fields follow predictable patterns. The Query-by-Committee algorithm instead identifies edge cases: clustered inclusions creating overlapping stress halos, narrow ligaments where stress gradients are steep, or unusual fiber arrangements that violate the assumptions learned from common configurations. Resolving these difficult cases early constrains the error space more effectively than accumulating redundant examples of typical geometries. The active learning curve demonstrates rapid initial improvement followed by stable convergence. The targeted querying approach maximizes the utility of the limited computational budget.

3.3 Inference Speed Comparison

Table 3 compares the per-evaluation runtime for FEA and the trained GNN surrogate. The GNN completes evaluations significantly faster than the baseline FEA approach.

Table 3: Per-evaluation runtime for FEA and the GNN surrogate

Method	Full Pipeline (s)	Inference Only (s)
FEA	0.507	0.504
GNN	0.011	0.0107
Speed Ratio	46.0:1	47.3:1

The baseline FEA pipeline includes mesh generation, assembly, and nonlinear solving. Pipeline steps create severe computational bottlenecks during iterative design tasks. The GNN bypasses conventional steps entirely by predicting fields directly from the graph structure. The reported timing comparison pits single-core FEA against GPU-accelerated GNN inference. A direct hardware-equivalent benchmark would

Figure 5: Visual comparison of FEA ground truth (left column) versus GNN predictions (center column) for a test microstructure: σ_{11} , σ_{22} , σ_{12} (stress, in MPa), u_x , and u_y (displacement, in mm). The right column shows point-wise prediction error.

yield a different raw ratio. The practical advantage remains the amortized query cost. Once trained, the surrogate evaluates thousands of geometries in seconds. Rapid inference transforms multi-objective optimization from a constrained local search into a comprehensive global mapping exercise. The comparison is not intended as a hardware-equivalent benchmark. The primary value is not raw wall-clock reduction but the ability to explore design spaces at a scale that would be logistically prohibitive with simulation-in-the-loop workflows. This efficiency transforms multi-objective optimization from a localized search into a global mapping exercise. Traditional methods rely on gradient-based optimizers that risk trapping the solution in local minima. The surrogate allows uniform sampling across the entire parameter grid. Designers can visualize the complete Pareto frontier rather than finding a single theoretical optimum. This broad mapping reveals the sharp performance cliffs documented in the subsequent sections. Finding these specific transition points requires dense sampling that only a fast surrogate can provide.

3.4 Multi-Task Architecture Benefits

An ablation study evaluated the single-model multi-task formulation against independent specialist models across five hidden dimensions. Figure S2 in Supplementary Information shows the full capacity comparison.

Figure S2 and Table 4 summarize the results. The multi-task model reduces matrix-phase σ_{11} RMSE by 33% and σ_{22} RMSE by 36% compared to the stress specialist at maximum capacity. The improvement does not stem from low-capacity regularization. Training multiple objectives simultaneously often risks negative transfer. Competing gradients frequently degrade overall model performance. The multi-task formulation avoids degradation and actively improves matrix-phase stress accuracy. For displacement fluctuations, multi-task and single-task models perform nearly identically, demonstrating no negative transfer from the stress tasks. Displacement fluctuations are heavily influenced by matrix compliance. Forcing the shared encoder to resolve compliance fluctuations prevents the representation from exclusively fitting the high-magnitude fiber stress targets. The network learns a more balanced physical representation of the entire composite domain. Similar

multi-task constraints could benefit future models incorporating thermal or moisture diffusion fields.

Table 4: Trainable parameter counts (in millions). The multi-task model requires approximately 38% fewer parameters than the combined specialists.

hidden_dim	Stress-Only	Disp-Only	ST Combined	Multi-Task
32	0.16M	0.16M	0.32M	0.20M
64	0.64M	0.65M	1.3M	0.79M
128	2.56M	2.58M	5.13M	3.16M
256	10.2M	10.3M	20.5M	12.6M
512	40.8M	41.0M	81.9M	50.4M

The multi-task model requires fewer parameters than the two specialists combined and produces all outputs in a single forward pass. For the large-scale exploration in this work, involving over 600,000 surrogate evaluations, this parameter reduction translates directly into reduced wall time.

3.5 Application-Specific Design Conflicts

Four independent Pareto analyses mapped effective stiffness against distinct damage initiation metrics. Because these initiation metrics rely on extreme-value spatial statistics, element-level prediction errors can potentially shift a design’s position on the Pareto frontier. To quantify this epistemic uncertainty, we computed the prediction variance across the $K=4$ ensemble for all Pareto-optimal designs. See Table S1 for more details.

3.5.1 Ranking Microstructures by Stress Concentration Factor

The stress concentration factor identifies peak matrix stress locations. Figure 6 presents the Pareto frontier for effective stiffness versus SCF. The maximum SCF of 1.40 observed on the Pareto frontier is a design space artifact resulting from the $0.2r$ minimum inter-fiber spacing constraint.

The maximum-stiffness design packs 14 fibers densely, leaving narrow matrix ligaments. Intense stress concentrations appear in these ligament regions. The minimum-SCF design uses 5 small, widely spaced fibers. The stress field demonstrates isolated perturbation zones. The balanced design utilizes 15 small fibers with sufficient spacing to prevent concentration zone overlap.

Table 5: Champion designs for stiffness vs. SCF.

Design	V_f	r (μm)	\bar{E} (GPa)	SCF
Max stiffness	0.51	10	83.9	1.40
Min SCF (wing)	0.10	5	24.3	1.05
Balanced	0.17	6	68.2	1.12

Designs requiring minimized SCF favor well-dispersed configurations. The physical mechanism is stress field isolation.

Figure 6: Pareto frontier for effective stiffness vs. stress concentration factor (SCF). Three champion designs highlight specific microstructural configurations. The frontier contains 32 non-dominated designs from 78,558 evaluated configurations. Effective stiffness ranges from 3.3 to 83.9 GPa; SCF spans 1.05 to 5.24.

Each fiber inclusion creates a localized stress perturbation in the surrounding matrix that decays with distance. When fibers are widely spaced, these perturbations decay before reaching neighboring inclusions, and the peak stress remains close to the single-fiber analytical solution. As fibers approach each other, their stress fields interact in the intervening ligament, amplifying the local stress concentration.

3.5.2 Ranking Microstructures by Yielding Path Fraction

The yielding path fraction V_{eff} quantifies planar stress percolation risk. Figure 7 displays the corresponding Pareto frontier.

The frontier contains 61 non-dominated designs and reveals a sharp stress contiguity transition. Below approximately 55 GPa, stress halos around individual fibers remain spatially isolated and matrix elements stay below the threshold ($V_{\text{eff}} = 0$). As stiffness increases beyond this point, the halos expand and merge into connected high-stress networks, producing the near-vertical cliff where V_{eff} jumps rapidly toward unity. This cliff suggests a stiffness threshold beyond which planar high-stress regions become connected; whether this corresponds to 3D failure path formation requires volumetric validation. These observations are limited to 2D planar connectivity and do not directly imply 3D through-thickness failure path formation.

The balanced design utilizes larger fiber radii, placing the stress halos at the edge of percolation. The minimum- V_{eff} design maintains small, isolated stress zones. Maintaining values below the stress contiguity transition requires restricted volume fractions and specific geometric spacing.

Figure 7: Pareto frontier for effective stiffness vs. yielding path fraction (V_{eff}). The frontier contains 61 non-dominated designs from 78,558 evaluated configurations. Effective stiffness ranges from 3.2 to 84.3 GPa; path fraction spans 0.0 to 1.0.

Table 6: Champion designs for stiffness vs. yielding path fraction.

Design	V_f	r (μm)	\bar{E} (GPa)	V_{eff}
Max stiffness	0.51	10	84.3	0.973
Min V_{eff} (PV)	0.20	5	48.1	0.000
Balanced	0.32	13	65.4	0.111

3.5.3 Ranking Microstructures by Interface Shear Density

Interface shear density measures tangential stress accumulated along phase boundaries. Figure 8 maps the frontier.

Figure 8: Pareto frontier for effective stiffness vs. interface shear density. The frontier contains 52 non-dominated designs from 78,558 evaluated configurations. Effective stiffness ranges from 3.2 to 84.3 GPa; interface shear density spans 0.76 to 13.1 GPa/m.

The maximum-stiffness design packs 14 fibers, generating extensive interface networks under high shear. The minimum-shear design uses only 4 large fibers, minimizing total interface perimeter per unit reinforcement area. Larger fibers achieve the same reinforcement volume with less total interface perimeter, directly reducing the accumulated shear along phase boundaries regardless of local stress intensity.

Table 7: Champion designs for stiffness vs. interface shear density.

Design	V_f	r (μm)	\bar{E} (GPa)	τ (GPa/m)
Max stiffness	0.51	10	84.3	6.87
Min debonding	0.13	14	17.7	0.76
Balanced	0.13	13	65.5	2.79

The comparison between the minimum-shear and balanced designs highlights material influence. Both utilize 4 fibers with similar radii. The observed difference arises from constituent material properties: stiffer matrices generate proportionally higher shear stresses along identical interface geometries. This establishes a design rule opposite to SCF and V_{eff} : minimizing interface shear favors fewer, larger fibers, whereas stress concentration and percolation mitigation favor smaller, dispersed inclusions. The geometric requirements for different failure modes are fundamentally incompatible.

3.5.4 Ranking Microstructures by Stress Triaxiality

Stress triaxiality η_{P95} quantifies the hydrostatic tension state within the matrix. Figure 9 presents the non-dominated designs under restricted configuration constraints ($V_f \geq 0.10$, $N \geq 5$).

Figure 9: Pareto frontier for effective stiffness vs. 95th-percentile stress triaxiality (η_{P95}). The analysis evaluates 57,233 configurations satisfying the volume fraction constraint ($V_f \geq 0.10$). The frontier contains 140 non-dominated designs. Effective stiffness ranges from 5.9 to 84.3 GPa; η_{P95} spans 0.407 to 0.995.

The metric η_{P95} never drops below 0.407 within the defined constraints. Every evaluated microstructure exhibits elevated hydrostatic states. Even the minimum-triaxiality design exhibits $\eta_{P95} > 0.4$, indicating that purely geometric optimization cannot eliminate cavitation susceptibility. The design question therefore shifts from eliminating high triaxiality to minimizing it while retaining useful stiffness. Unlike the previous three applications, cryogenic tank design requires accepting elevated triaxiality and compensating through material selection. Utilizing cryogenic-grade matrix materials with enhanced cavitation resistance remains essential.

Table 8: Champion designs for stiffness vs. triaxiality trade-off.

Design	V_f	r (μm)	\bar{E} (GPa)	η_{P95}
Max stiffness	0.51	10	84.3	0.986
Min triaxiality	0.10	5	5.9	0.407
Balanced	0.10	5	34.3	0.611

The dominant design variable for cavitation resistance is fiber radius, not fiber count. Smaller fibers reduce local constraint and create compact Poisson constraint zones to lower triaxiality, but at the cost of reduced stiffness. This intrinsic trade-off produces the smooth, monotonic frontier observed, indicating that increased stiffness directly elevates hydrostatic metrics. Table 9 consolidates the optimal designs for each individual application.

3.5.5 Global Multi-Objective Synthesis

We computed a global Pareto rank across all four metrics simultaneously for configurations exceeding a stiffness baseline of $\bar{E} > 58.1$ GPa. Figure 10 maps these filtered designs.

The Global Best design balances all four damage initiation metrics while maintaining baseline stiffness. The stiffness threshold eliminates microstructures offering high damage resistance but insufficient structural rigidity. Analyzing the remaining high-performance geometries requires evaluating all four initiation metrics simultaneously. The global Pareto rank mathematically sorts designs based on simultaneous non-dominance across all objectives. A rank-one design is not outperformed by any other geometry across the complete metric suite. Designers utilize ranked configurations when the governing operational failure mode remains undefined. For cases where volume fraction is constrained by external requirements like weight, cost, or manufacturability, we binned designs by V_f in increments of 0.05 and identified the champion within each bin. These binned optima provide practical design rules: given a required volume fraction, the corresponding marker indicates the fiber radius that minimizes aggregate failure risk.

This global synthesis reveals a hidden challenge in heuristic composite design. Consider two microstructures with identi-

cal fiber count and radius but different spatial arrangements: they appear geometrically similar, yet their failure metrics can differ by factors of two or more due to differences in fiber clustering and load-path formation. Geometric similarity does not guarantee mechanical equivalence. This variability is invisible to traditional design approaches relying on geometric intuition alone. A designer selecting microstructures based on fiber count and radius would have no way to distinguish high-performing from low-performing configurations within the same geometric class. The high-throughput surrogate screening executed here is essential precisely because it exposes this hidden variability.

3.6 Learned Representation Analysis

We extracted 2048-dimensional embeddings and projected them using UMAP [55]. Figure 11 colors these projections by stiffness, volume fraction, and peak matrix stress.

The embedding organizes into distinct clusters rather than a continuous manifold, with smooth property gradients visible within each cluster. Designs with similar effective stiffness and volume fraction map to neighboring regions regardless of their specific geometric arrangement, indicating that the network has learned to group microstructures by mechanical response rather than visual appearance. The stiffness gradient and volume fraction gradient are correlated but not identical. This means that the high volume fraction generally produces high stiffness, but the spread within each cluster shows that fiber arrangement and material properties also contribute. The peak stress coloring shows more scatter, reflecting the sensitivity of extreme stress values to local geometric details that are partially averaged out in bulk properties. This organization confirms that the latent representation captures physically meaningful structure: the network distinguishes microstructures by how they distribute load, not simply by how many fibers they contain.

3.7 Homogenization Accuracy

Effective stiffness moduli were computed from GNN-predicted stress and strain fields. Validation datasets included in-distribution configurations and out-of-distribution (OOD) geometries.

Both datasets show tight clustering along the true diagonal (Figure 12). The surrogate provides reliable bulk property estimation alongside local field predictions. Accurate local field prediction must translate to reliable macroscopic property estimation. Multiscale structural simulations require accurate homogenized moduli to model component-level behavior. Classical homogenization methods accurately predict bulk properties but erase the localized stress concentrations driving damage initiation. The surrogate approach preserves the local concentration data while successfully recovering the bulk stiffness tensor.

Table 9: Application-specific optimal designs from the four independent Pareto analyses.

Application	Initiation Metric	V_f	r (μm)	\bar{E} (GPa)	Metric Value
Airplane Wings	Min SCF	0.10	5	24.3	1.05
Pressure Vessels	Min V_{eff}	0.20	5	48.1	0.000
Wind Turbines	Min $\tau_{\text{interface}}$	0.13	14	17.7	0.76
Cryogenic Tanks	Min η_{P95}	0.13	5	5.9	0.407

Figure 10: Global Multi-Objective Synthesis mapping designs in the V_f - r space, colored by global Pareto rank.

Figure 11: UMAP projection of GNN embeddings. Panels show the same projection colored by effective stiffness, volume fraction, and peak matrix stress.

Figure 12: Homogenization parity plots comparing predicted moduli against FEA ground truth.

The success of homogenization despite local prediction errors reflects the nature of volume averaging. Homogenized stiffness is computed by integrating stress over the entire domain, which smooths local fluctuations. The slight over- or under-prediction of stress near fiber-matrix interfaces has minimal impact on the integrated result because these errors are spatially localized and do not bias the domain-averaged stress in a particular direction. The strong out-of-distribution performance demonstrates robust scaling. The MT-GNN can therefore serve as a surrogate within multiscale frameworks, providing both full-field responses and homogenized properties in a single forward pass.

3.8 Manufacturing Robustness

Sensitivity studies investigated material property variations and geometric variations. Figure 13 illustrates the perturbations.

Figure 13: Manufacturing variability study comparing material property variations against geometric centroid shifts.

Within the perturbation ranges studied ($\pm 5\%$ fiber position shifts, $\pm 5\%$ fiber modulus, $\pm 10\%$ matrix modulus), material property variations produce $9\times$ more performance variability

than geometric variations for the metrics considered. This asymmetry has a clear physical origin. Fiber position perturbations redistribute where stress concentrations occur within the RVE, but they do not fundamentally alter the load-carrying architecture: the fibers still carry the majority of axial load, and the matrix still transfers shear between inclusions. A fiber shifted by 5% of its radius creates a local stress redistribution, but the volume-averaged mechanical response remains similar because the global topology is preserved.

Material property variations operate differently. Changing the matrix modulus by 10% alters the stiffness contrast ratio between phases throughout the entire domain simultaneously. This contrast ratio governs how load partitions between fiber and matrix. A stiffer matrix carries more load directly, reducing the stress concentration at interfaces, while a softer matrix forces more load through the fibers and amplifies interface stresses. The effect is global rather than local, which explains why small material variations produce large performance swings. For the perturbation ranges studied, investing in consistent resin batch properties and controlled curing conditions will reduce performance variability more effectively than tighter tolerances on fiber placement equipment. This finding applies to the micro-scale geometric variations analyzed here; macro-scale defects such as dry spots, voids, or large resin-rich regions remain critical concerns that require separate quality assurance protocols.

4 Discussion

That different applications require different composite microstructures is well understood. What has been missing are quantitative answers: how different must they be, what specific parameters matter, and what is the cost of compromise?

This work provides partial quantitative insight into these questions for elastic stress response; extending to inelastic failure requires further validation.

The Pareto analyses reveal that optimal microstructures tend to occupy distinct regions of the design space. Airplane wings and pressure vessels favor small fibers for different physical reasons: suppressing extreme concentrations versus preventing contiguous high-stress planar regions. Wind turbines demand large fibers to minimize interface perimeter. Cryogenic tanks require low volume fractions to limit Poisson constraints. No single microstructure minimizes all damage initiation metrics simultaneously. Across the explored design space, fewer than 0.2% of configurations lie on the Pareto front for any given metric, ranging from 32 non-dominated designs for SCF to 140 for triaxiality. This sparsity underscores why large-scale exploration is necessary, as a conventional parametric study of 50 to 100 simulations would likely miss optimal configurations entirely. This variation in front size also reflects the underlying design landscape: SCF has sharp, narrow optima while triaxiality presents a smoother trade-off surface with more equivalent solutions.

The framework makes large-scale analysis tractable. Once trained, the GNN evaluates new designs in 0.01 seconds, enabling exploration of 78,558 microstructures. Exploring such a massive design space resolved sharp transitions like the stress contiguity cliff.

The multi-task formulation improved matrix-phase stress accuracy compared to a stress-only specialist. The shared encoder is constrained by displacement outputs, preventing representation drift toward high-magnitude fiber targets. Query-by-Committee active learning reduced the FEA data requirement by concentrating the simulation budget on high-uncertainty regions.

The graph-native representation offers structural advantages over grid-based alternatives. Convolutional neural networks require interpolating unstructured finite element meshes onto regular voxel grids, which blurs the sharp stress gradients at fiber-matrix interfaces that govern damage initiation. The GNN operates directly on mesh topology, preserving these critical features without resolution loss from resampling.

Several limitations bound the current findings. The analysis is restricted to two-dimensional plane-strain RVEs; real composites are three-dimensional with additional failure modes including fiber breakage, out-of-plane delamination, and through-thickness stress gradients. The GNN architecture generalizes to 3D meshes without modification, but generating 3D training data requires minutes to hours per simulation, making the active learning loop substantially more expensive. The constitutive models are purely elastic, so no plasticity, damage accumulation, viscoelasticity, or time-dependent degradation is captured. Applied strains were limited to 3%, keeping the

response in the small-deformation regime despite the Neo-Hookean matrix formulation. The four failure metrics are physics-based proxies for damage initiation rather than formal failure criteria; they identify dominant initiation mechanisms but do not directly predict cycles-to-failure, time-to-debonding, or residual strength. Macro-scale manufacturing defects such as voids, resin-rich regions, or severe fiber clustering were not included. The manufacturing robustness findings apply only to the perturbation ranges analyzed: $\pm 5\%$ fiber position shifts, $\pm 5\%$ fiber modulus variation, and $\pm 10\%$ matrix modulus variation.

The methodology transfers to other heterogeneous material systems where elastic stress pre-screening can inform design rankings.

5 Conclusions

This work introduces a Multi-Task Graph Neural Network surrogate for full-field stress prediction in fiber-reinforced composite microstructures. The architecture processes unstructured finite element meshes directly, avoiding the interpolation artifacts inherent in grid-based approaches. The multi-task formulation improved matrix-phase stress accuracy by over 30% compared to single-task specialists, while Query-by-Committee active learning reduced training data requirements by 40%.

The surrogate enabled screening of 78,558 microstructure designs across four damage initiation metrics. The Pareto analyses reveal that optimal configurations for different applications occupy distinct geometric regions: pressure vessels and airplane wings favor small, dispersed fibers; wind turbines require large fibers to minimize interface area; cryogenic tanks demand low volume fractions to limit triaxial constraint. No universal microstructure optimizes all metrics simultaneously. The 55 GPa stiffness threshold for yielding path percolation and the material-dominated manufacturing sensitivity provide actionable constraints for composite design. The broader contribution is not the specific design rules for these four applications, but the demonstration that such rules exist, are quantitatively accessible through surrogate-driven exploration, and conflict in ways that cannot be resolved by a single generic microstructure specification. Several findings reported here, including the 55 GPa percolation threshold for stress path connectivity, the opposing geometric requirements across failure modes, and the absence of any cavitation-safe configuration within realistic manufacturing constraints, emerge only through dense sampling of the design space. These insights would be inaccessible using conventional simulation-in-the-loop optimization, which typically evaluates tens to hundreds of candidates rather than tens of thousands.

The methodology, consisting of a multi-task GNN with active learning, large-scale Pareto analysis, and application-

specific failure metrics, transfers to any heterogeneous material system where competing applications impose different mechanical demands, those demands can be expressed as field-level metrics, and high-fidelity simulation is too expensive for direct exploration. 3D woven composites, polycrystalline metals, porous ceramics, and particle-reinforced polymers are all candidates. Only the training data and failure metric definitions need to change. The damage initiation metrics are not failure predictors; extending to propagation-dominated failure requires progressive damage modeling beyond the current elastic framework. Three-dimensional validation and experimental correlation remain necessary before deployment in certification workflows.

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Supplementary Information

Figure S1: Active learning ablation study. Test set RMSE versus training data size for all five output fields, comparing Query-by-Committee active learning against random sampling.

Figure S2: Multi-task architecture ablation. Test set RMSE versus model capacity comparing single-task specialists against the multi-task model.

Figure S3: Parity plots for all five output fields on the held-out test set, shown separately for fiber and matrix phases. Dashed line indicates perfect prediction.

Figure S4: Displacement fluctuation predictions ($u_{x,fluc}$, $u_{y,fluc}$) for a representative test sample. Left: FEA ground truth. Center: GNN prediction. Right: absolute error.

Figure S5: Full-field predictions for all five output fields on a representative test sample. Columns: FEA ground truth, GNN prediction, absolute error. Black circles denote fiber boundaries.

Figure S6: Prediction accuracy distribution for σ_{11} across the test set. Rows show samples at selected RMSE percentiles. RMSE is computed as a percentage of within-sample field range.

Metric	Frontier Size	Median CV (%)
SCF	32	2.2
Triaxiality	140	5.8
Interface Shear	52	13.3
V_{eff}	61	37.5

Table S1: Ensemble prediction uncertainty for Pareto-optimal designs computed from $K = 4$ ensemble members. SCF and triaxiality exhibit low variance (median CV $< 6\%$), indicating reliable rankings. Interface shear shows moderate variance. V_{eff} exhibits elevated variance because the metric requires both identifying elements exceeding a 1500 MPa stress threshold and computing connected component size; small stress perturbations near the threshold can shift a design from isolated to connected regions, causing large metric changes. This sensitivity reflects the physical sharpness of the percolation transition, the same mechanism that produces the cliff in Figure 7. The existence of the percolation transition and its approximate location near 55 GPa is consistent across all ensemble members; quantitative V_{eff} rankings near the transition should be interpreted with caution.

Hyperparameter	Value
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate	1×10^{-4}
Batch size	8
Training epochs	100
Hidden dimension	128
GATv2 layers	4
Attention heads per layer	4
Ensemble size (K)	4
<i>Active Learning</i>	
Initial training pool	600 graphs
Candidates per iteration	5
Candidate pool size	100
Load cases per AL query	15

Table S2: Training hyperparameters for the MT-GNN model.